

dia meltada meltada (Gray) cause severe damage to the rice crop in Aduthurai. Rodents' preference for rice varieties was observed during 1981 kharif. Recommended management practices were followed in 5- × 4-m test plots replicated 3 times.

Rodent damage was assessed 65 days after transplanting. Total tillers and rat cut tillers were counted on 20 hills selected at random along a transect through the middle of each plot.

Of the 57 varieties observed, IET5742 had no rat damage and 21 varieties had less than 5% damage (see table). Jaya, which is susceptible to many insect pests, also had the highest rodent damage (35.4%). □

TABLE CONTINUED

Variety	Damage (%)	Variety	Damage (%)	Variety	Damage (%)
IET6441	3.4	IR20	6.6	IET6276	10.0
IET5914	3.5	TNAU20216	6.7	IET6314	10.4
PY 1	3.6	IET5975	6.7	IET6271	10.8
IET6264	3.8	IET6658	7.0	IET6282	11.4
IET7046	3.9	IET6272	7.1	IET6466	12.3
IET6686	4.1	IET6657	7.2	IET20-H	27-97 12.7
IET6987	4.5	IET6666	7.9	IET6669	12.8
Bhavani	4.8	IET5890	8.0	IET6279	13.5
IET6290	4.8	Pankaj	8.5	IET6269	14.5
AS781/1	4.8	IET6265	8.6	IET6144	15.2
IET6263	5.2	IET6074	8.8	IET3231	15.5
IET5882	5.6	IET6212	8.8	TM3802	15.8
ADT35	6.2	IET7041	9.1	IET6262	16.0
IET6261	6.6	IET5883	9.7	IET6010	21.4
		Jagannath	9.8	Jaya	35.4
				IET5709	44.4

^aAv of 3 replications.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Screening for quick establishment and submergence tolerance at seedling stage

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Ill-drained wetlands make up most of the riceland in Bihar. Although their natural soil fertility is high, they are affected by many stress conditions such as a sudden rise in water level in the transplanted fields because of the July-August rains. Crops are washed out and the percentage of stand is reduced. Transplanting must sometimes be delayed until mid-September, when yield recovery is marginal. Varieties with good seedling submergence tolerance and quick stand establishment are needed for these areas.

On 2 September 1980, 40-day-old seedlings of 48 F₅ cultures from the cross Borogar (deepwater)/IR8//BR14 (deepwater); 7 F₅ culture from Borogar/IR8; and 46 mixed cultures comprising local deepwater, wetland, and introduced materials were transplanted in a typical wetland field. Each culture had 6 rows of 22 plants/row and 1 seedling/hill transplanted at a 20- × 15-cm spacing. Two days later, water began to rise, reaching 40- to

50-cm depth. Only the leaf tips of a few cultures remained visible during this period; almost all plants were submerged.

When the water receded 10 days later, the surviving plants were counted. Many cultivars that looked dead were, in fact, alive and later gave shoots. Some also showed adventitious roots. Varietal differences in surviving stands varied from 0 to 66%. Twelve of the 48 cultures of Borogar/IR8//BR14 were wiped out; 10

had more than 20% survival. Six of the seven cultures of Borogar/IR8 had 27-47% survival. Among the deepwater types, only three — C183 (Akalbir), C180-6 (Singhra), and Parwapankh — had more than 20% survival. Locally adopted deepwater types such as Kabra, Bajra, Janeria, Borogar, Jagnathia, Pichar, and the introduced lines CN539, CN540, CN63, CN643, and CR1105 performed poorly. Five cultures were superior (see table). □

Characteristic features of superior submergence-tolerant rice cultures. Bhagalpur, India.

Cultivar	Cross	Survival (%)	Feature	Tillers/plant (av no.)	Grain type	Kernel color
1-246	Borogar/IR8//BR14	40	Dwarf	7.5	Short bold	Red
56-19-22	Borogar/IR8//BR14	66	Medium dwarf	8.2	Short bold	White or red
6-13-35	Borogar/IR8	45	Tall	8.0	Medium bold	White
7-15-34	Borogar/IR8	47	Tall	9.7	Short bold	White
C183	Pureline selections from Akalbir	42	Tall	5.8	Medium bold	White

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